

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

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APPLICATION OF EXTREME MODELS IN ASSESSING THE ECONOMIC POTENTIAL OF AN ENTERPRISE

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Abstract. This article examines optimization models used to assess the economic potential of enterprises. Particular attention is given to maintaining a rational balance between the production volumes of different product groups, the efficiency of finished product sales, and the level of finished goods inventories. The study analyzes how optimization approaches can support more effective management decisions and improve overall enterprise performance.

Key words: enterprise, optimization, profitability, efficiency, model, method.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada korxonalarining iqtisodiy salohiyatini baholash uchun qo'llaniladigan optimallashtirish modellari ko'rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqotda turli mahsulot guruhlarini ishlab chiqarish hajmlari, tayyor mahsulotlarni sotish samaradorligi hamda tayyor mahsulot zaxiralari darajasi o'rtasidagi oqilona muvozanatni ta'minlash masalalari tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, optimallashtirish yondashuvlari korxonalar faoliyatining samaradorligini oshirish va boshqaruv qarorlarini takomillashtirishga xizmat qilishi asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: korxonalar, optimallashtirish, rentabellik, samaradorlik, model, usul.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются оптимизационные модели оценки экономического потенциала предприятия. Особое внимание уделяется обеспечению рационального соотношения между объемами выпуска различных групп продукции, эффективностью реализации готовой продукции и уровнем запасов готовой продукции. Также анализируются возможности применения оптимизационных подходов для повышения эффективности деятельности предприятия и совершенствования управленческих решений.

Ключевые слова: предприятие, оптимизация, рентабельность, эффективность, модель, метод.

INTRODUCTION

Assessing the economic potential of an enterprise is an important element of strategic planning, financial analysis, and managerial decision-making. In an increasingly competitive and dynamic economic environment, the development and application of optimization models that comprehensively take into account production, labor, sales, and financial factors are becoming particularly important.

Optimization models for evaluating economic potential make it possible to formalize complex multi-criteria problems and determine the most efficient options for the development and utilization of an enterprise's resources. Classical optimization approaches are based on linear and nonlinear programming methods, as well as on the theory of constraints (Goldratt, 1990)¹.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Mathematical programming is one of the most widely used approaches in assessing the economic potential of an enterprise. According to Z. A. Petelin (2019)², this approach is based on formulating objective functions, such as profit maximization or cost minimization, while introducing constraints that reflect production, sales, financial, and resource limitations.

1 Goldratt EM The Goal: A Process of Ongoing Improvement. – 2nd ed. – Great Barrington, MA: North River Press, 1990. – 337 p.

2 Petelin Zh. A. Mathematical methods in economics. - M.: Infra-M, 2019.

Multifactor models also play an important role in assessing economic potential. In the works of I. Yu. Levina (2020)³, particular attention is given to the construction of models that take into account more than 20 factors influencing economic potential, using factor analysis and regression modeling methods.

Simulation and scenario modeling are applied to analyze the stability of economic potential under conditions of uncertainty. This approach is reflected in the research of N. V. Shakhova (2021)⁴, who emphasizes the importance of forecasting possible changes in enterprise performance under different economic scenarios.

In recent years, intelligent systems, including artificial intelligence and neural networks, have become increasingly relevant in this field. For example, in the studies of A. N. Kotlyarov (2022)⁵, the application of machine learning methods is analyzed for predicting changes in economic potential based on large volumes of production and financial data.

A review of the scientific literature shows that there is a wide range of approaches to assessing the economic potential of an enterprise. Researchers generally interpret economic potential as an integrated characteristic that reflects the totality of material, labor, and financial resources, as well as the enterprise's ability to use them effectively both in the current period and in the strategic future.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employed a systematic approach to analyze the economic potential of enterprises and to identify optimal management solutions. Within the framework of the research, marketing analysis, benchmarking, and the use of digital metrics were applied to evaluate enterprise performance and compare it with industry standards.

In addition, mass observation methods were used to collect and analyze relevant information from open digital sources and social media platforms. The collected data were processed using comparative and analytical techniques, which made it possible to identify key trends, evaluate influencing factors, and determine the effectiveness of optimization models in improving enterprise performance and resource utilization.

ANALYSIS END RESULTS

The main objective of the optimization model is to maximize the net profit of the enterprise. This implies identifying the most effective allocation of available resources and determining an optimal sales planning strategy that ensures the highest possible financial return.

Within the framework of the model, the system evaluates different combinations of production volumes, resource utilization, and sales structures in order to identify the solution that provides the maximum difference between total revenue from product sales and all associated costs. Such costs include production expenses, logistics, labor, and other operational expenditures.

The results of the analysis show that the application of optimization models allows enterprises to improve production planning, balance product group outputs, and maintain efficient inventory levels. As a result, the enterprise can enhance profitability, ensure more rational use of resources, and strengthen its overall economic potential.

Mathematically, the objective function is formulated as follows:

$$\text{Maximize } Z = \sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - C_i - M_i - D_i) * Q_i$$

Where:

Z — objective function (net profit);

n — number of product names (or areas of activity);

P_i — selling price of a unit of output;

C_i — production cost per unit of output;

M_i — marketing costs per unit of production;

3 Levina I. Yu. Assessment and modeling of the economic potential of an industrial enterprise // Bulletin of Economics and Law. - 2020. - No. 2

4 Shakhova N.V. Scenario analysis in enterprise potential management // Management in Russia and abroad. - 2021. - No. 1.

5 Kotlyarov A. N. Forecasting economic indicators based on neural network models // Artificial intelligence and decision making. - 2022. - No. 3.

D_i — sales and logistics costs per unit of production;

Q_i — volume of product sales.

Each term in the sum reflects the net profit from the sale of a specific product. This is the profit per unit of product multiplied by its sales volume. As a possible modification of the model, if taxes are taken into account

in the economy, a tax coefficient can be included in the model: $(P_i - C_i - M_i - D_i) * Q_i * t$

$$\text{Maximize } Z = (1 - t) \sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - C_i - M_i - D_i) * Q_i$$

Production factors describe a company's ability to produce products. They include raw material resource constraints, equipment production capacity, and product mix balance.

Raw materials. One of the key factors limiting a company's production activity is the availability and accessibility of raw materials. Each product requires a certain volume of various raw materials, the supply of which is limited both in absolute terms and in terms of replenishment rates. To ensure the realistic nature of the production plan, a limit on raw material consumption is imposed.

Mathematically, this condition is written as follows:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n R_{ij} * Q_i \leq S_j + R_j^{upd}, \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, k$$

- R_{ij} — standard consumption of raw materials of type j per unit of output i ;
- Q_i — the planned volume of output of product type i ;
- S_j — current stocks of raw materials j ;
- R_j^{upd} — the volume of receipts of raw materials of type j during the planning period;
- k — total number of types of raw materials;
- n — the total number of product types.

The essence of this constraint is that we cannot produce more products than our existing and incoming raw materials allow. Each unit of production requires a certain quantity of each type of raw material, and the total consumption across all types of products must not exceed the available volume.

Equipment restrictions. Within a comprehensive model for assessing an enterprise's economic potential, equipment constraints can be represented through the limited operational life of the equipment in time terms. This approach allows for consideration of not only nominal capacities but also the actual production load of the equipment.

Mathematically, the constraint is formulated as follows:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n t_{ij} * Q_i \leq T_j^{avail}, \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, m$$

Where:

- Q_i — the volume of manufactured products of type i ;
- t_{ij} — the cost of machine time for the production of one unit of product i on equipment of type j ;
- T_j^{avail} — the available operating time fund of equipment of type j for the billing period;
- n — number of product types;
- m — number of equipment types.

The economic interpretation of this limitation is to ensure that the planned equipment load matches its actual capacity. This prevents load redistribution beyond permissible time limits, taking into account the work schedule, technical condition, shift patterns, and scheduled maintenance.

This approach makes the model more flexible and closer to the actual operating conditions of production equipment, especially in the presence of a mixed product range and limited technological resources.

Limitation on the product range structure. In a multi-product manufacturing environment, maintaining a rational balance between the output volumes of various product groups is an important planning element. This constraint ensures a stable supply structure that meets market demands, the company's internal priorities, logistics, and production capabilities.

A product range limitation is introduced as a proportional relationship between the output volumes of different product types. Mathematically, it can be written as:

$$\beta_{min} \leq \frac{Q_a}{Q_b} \leq \beta_{max}$$

Where:

- Q_a, Q_b — the volumes of production of products of types a and b, between which it is necessary to maintain a proportion;
- β_{min}, β_{max} — the lower and upper limits of the permissible ratio between the corresponding output volumes.

This condition ensures:

- balance of supply and demand within various product categories;
- maintaining competitive positions in each area;
- uniform loading of technological lines;
- alignment with corporate strategy (e.g. prioritizing the production of highly profitable or innovative products).

If the enterprise's product range includes more than two key groups, this constraint can be generalized to a system of proportional ratios, or replaced by a condition on the output structure using weighting coefficients:

$$\gamma_j^{min} Q_{total} \leq Q_i \leq \gamma_j^{max} Q_{total}, \forall j=1, \dots, k$$

Where:

Q_i — the volume of output of product i;

$Q_{total} = \sum_{i=1}^n Q_i$ — the total volume of all manufactured products;

$\gamma_j^{min}, \gamma_j^{max}$

— минимально и максимально допустимая доля группы j в общем выпуске;

k — количество ассортиментных групп;

This condition allows:

- control the structure of the production program;
- prevent imbalances between product lines;
- adhere to the marketing strategy (for example, maintain the premium segment at least 30%, but not more than 50%);
- flexibly scale the model as the number of products or product range changes.

Thus, assortment limitation plays the role of a regulator of the production profile and contributes to the stability of both the operational and sales circuits of the enterprise.

An enterprise's sales subsystem serves as a key link between the production system and the market. The effectiveness of finished product sales directly impacts revenue, capital turnover, logistics costs, and, consequently, the overall economic potential of the enterprise.

The optimization model takes into account the following key constraints and parameters related to sales:

Limitations on warehouse capacity for finished products. Finished product warehousing is a crucial element in the material flow chain from production to the consumer. Limited warehouse capacity requires efficient inventory management, especially in the face of unstable demand, seasonal fluctuations, or shipping delays.

To formalize the constraint, the following mathematical relationship is used:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n Q_i V_i \leq W_{ready}$$

Q_i — the volume of production (or output) of products of type i subject to storage;

V_i — specific warehouse volume per unit of product of type i (in m^3 , m^2 , pallet places, etc.);

W_{ready} — total available storage capacity of finished goods warehouses;

n is the number of product types.

This limitation reflects the need to consider the physical limits of warehouse infrastructure. It prevents overproduction, which could lead to overstocking, spoilage of goods (especially perishables), increased storage costs, or forced storage using unconventional methods (such as open-air storage).

Ensuring the standard level of finished product inventories. For a company to operate reliably, it's important not only to produce and sell products in a timely manner, but also to maintain a certain standard level of inventory in the warehouse. Such inventory is necessary for:

- compensation for fluctuations in demand;
- ensuring uninterrupted shipments;
- reservation of products for long-term contracts;
- reducing risks due to logistics disruptions.

From a mathematical point of view, the minimum stock condition is expressed as follows:

$$Q_i^{stock} \geq Z_i^{norm}, \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, n$$

Q_i^{stock} — фактический объём запаса готовой продукции типа i на складе;

Z_i^{norm} — нормативный (страховой) уровень запаса для продукции i ;

n — number of product types.

If the stock is formed due to the difference between the output of products and their sales in the current period, then:

$$Q_i^{prod} - Q_i^{sell} \geq Z_i^{norm}, \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, n$$

Where:

Q_i^{prod} — volume of manufactured products;

Q_i^{sell} — volume of shipped (sold) products;

This limitation ensures that the warehouse always has the minimum product buffer necessary for uninterrupted operations. If this buffer is not maintained, the company risks losing orders due to unavailable items, especially during sudden surges in demand or logistics delays.

Financial constraints play a central role in the development of a realistic optimization model. They define the boundaries within which a company can carry out production, sales, investment, and marketing without losing stability and solvency.

A company must maintain the ability to meet its current financial obligations in a timely manner. Within the optimization model, this constraint serves as a financial stability criterion, preventing cash flow shortfalls and reducing the risk of bankruptcy. Even with high gross profit, a company may become insolvent if cash receipts are late or fail to cover current obligations. Therefore, the model must consider the relationship between incoming and outgoing cash flows within the calculation period.

Mathematical formalization:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n R_i^{in} - \sum_{j=1}^n R_j^{out} \geq L_{min}$$

Where:

R_i^{in} — expected cash flow from source i (e.g. sales revenue, customer advances, subsidies, loans), $i=1, \dots, n$;

R_j^{out} — mandatory payments in direction j (for example, salary, taxes, rent, utility bills, debt servicing), $j=1, \dots, m$;

L_{min} — the minimum acceptable cash balance that ensures liquidity (specified in absolute terms or as a percentage of expenses).

The economic rationale behind the solvency equation is to ensure a stable cash balance for an enterprise over the planned horizon. It reflects the requirement that the sum of all expected cash inflows (sales revenue, loans, advances, other income) be sufficient to cover all mandatory operating expenses (salaries, taxes, rent, utilities, purchases of raw materials and supplies, etc.), and also provide a reserve equal to the minimum cash balance required for financial stability. Thus, the solvency constraint is not simply a technical requirement, but a fundamental financial filter, ensuring that all decisions within the model are consistent with the actual financial viability of the enterprise. L_{min}

Limitation on product profitability. Product profitability reflects the efficiency of production and sales of each product type. It shows the share of profit a company receives from each unit of investment. In the optimization model, this constraint serves as a filter, excluding the production and sale of low-efficiency or unprofitable products. Even if a certain product is technically feasible and marketable, its production may not meet the company's financial goals if its profitability is below the established minimum. Including a profitability constraint ensures the economic viability of the entire production program.

Formal definition of profitability per unit of output. For each position $i=1, 2, \dots, n$ the profitability is calculated as:

$$Rent_i = \frac{P_i - C_i - M_i - D_i}{C_i + M_i + D_i}$$

Where:

- $Rent_i$ — profitability of product i ;
- P_i — selling price of a unit of output;
- C_i — production cost per unit of output;
- M_i — marketing costs per unit of production;
- D_i — sales and logistics costs per unit of production;

Mathematical formalization of the constraint:

$$Rent_i \geq Rent_i^{min}, \text{ Where } \forall i \in S$$

$Rent_i^{min}$ — минимально допустимый уровень рентабельности по изделию i ;

S — a subset of products to which profitability control applies (possibly not to all types).

The practical significance of this constraint lies in eliminating unprofitable or marginally inefficient products from the production program, ensuring a minimum level of profitability when utilizing production capacity, and simplifying product mix decisions: we produce only those that generate an acceptable profit. A possible extension of the model is the use of the weighted average profitability of finished goods:

$$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n ((P_i - C_i - M_i - D_i) * Q_i)}{(\sum_{i=1}^n (C_i + M_i + D_i) * Q_i)} \geq R^{avg-min}$$

Where is the acceptable minimum weighted average profitability for the entire product range. $R^{avg-min}$

The profitability constraint makes the model not simply one that optimizes profit, but one that selects a production structure with the required level of efficiency.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The analysis shows that the combination of the presented constraints forms a realistic model that reflects the key resources and operational limitations of an enterprise. This approach provides both a mathematical foundation and practical applicability for strategic planning and for optimizing production and sales programs.

The developed model makes it possible to integrate strategic and operational indicators within a single mathematical framework. Such integration improves the accuracy of planning, supports rational resource allocation, and enhances the overall efficiency of enterprise management.

For practical implementation, the model can be applied using modern analytical tools and software platforms, including Microsoft Excel, Python (using libraries such as PuLP, Pyomo, and Gurobi), R (using the LPSolve library), or other specialized optimization environments. The use of these tools allows enterprises to perform flexible modeling, analyze alternative scenarios, and select the most effective development strategies.

Overall, the proposed approach provides a quantitatively grounded method for evaluating the economic potential of enterprises and supports informed managerial decisions aimed at improving profitability, operational efficiency, and sustainable development.

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